

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NJAMBONG****FIRST NAME: GUY****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP:

1. Research topic/paper (EUCLID 2019, 2)
2. Essay/papers writing (EUCLID 2019, 1, 14-16)
3. Literature review (EUCLID 2019,5-6)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
5. Citation (EUCLID 2019, 6-11)
6. Referencing (EUCLID 2019, 4, 11, 12)
7. Critical thinking (EUCLID 2019, 2)
8. Style and usage (EUCLID 2019, 44-49)

HONOR ELDERS TO DISCOVER NEW SUBSTANCE

1) INTRODUCTION

In the public health academic world, considered an “applied social sciences” (Badgley et al. 1963, 147), one can discuss how students challenge and appropriate concepts and then innovate in their work? This discussion is essential if we consider that public health is increasingly involved with informing, educating, and supporting the population’s new behavior about specific health issues (1963, 152). Nowadays, with COVID-19 “causing commotion among the medical community and the rest of the world” (Palacios Cruz et al. 2020), the stake is higher. It was already highly complicated for Africa when we take stock of the deadly Ebola outbreak (Weyer, Grobbelaar, and Blumberg 2015, 7) or the destructuring impact of HIV (Luboobi and Mugisha 2005) but mainly the still devastating Malaria (Snow 2015, 1).

a) Online Public Health Education in Africa is a Solution

As stated by Shelton et al. (2018, 1), a significant trend is to increase the public health workforce number and implementing adapted solutions to train them. As said by

Rabbani et al. (2016), Schools of public health in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC)s “can contribute to overcoming several public health challenges.” For instance, the influence of the master of public health (MPH) programs in “contributing to health system strengthening in LMIC” was positively considerable (Zwanikken, Alexander, and Scherpbier 2016, 1). In Australia, the MPH curriculum now has indigenous courses (Angus, Ewen, and Coombe 2016, 1). This kind of information is crucial for Africa, which in the healthcare workforce “is relatively deprived compared to the rest of the world” (Ijsselmuiden et al. 2007, cited in Agyepong et al. 2018, ii36).

To deep dive into the African university context, some studies can inform us: Firstly, to start solving the lack of training in some French-speaking countries in Africa, the University of Geneva implemented an e-learning MPH (e-MPH). Chastonay et al. (2015, 6) discovered that one of the issues is **plagiarism**. Secondly, for an e-MPH at the National School of Public Health in South Africa, a lack of computer skills was a significant issue (Mokwena et al. 2007, 952). Thirdly, the case of the University of Cape Town's MPH helps us understand that the centrality to pursue such a program in Africa was to develop **critical** thinking skills (Zweigenthal, Marquez, and London 2016, 4). This centrality is the same for some UK universities where the commonly perceived skills for a master's in international public health (MIPH) were **critical** analysis (Buunaaisie et al. 2018, 1). Simultaneously, in the UK, the People-Uni e-MPH program, focusing on students from LMIC, reached such a goal - but is not yet accredited (Sridharan et al. 2018, 1).

As for Euclid University in Central Africa, which has an accredited online MIPH, and which I recently joined, having good **writing** skills is essential. It is visible through the curriculum's first course, "international academic and professional paper writing" (Euclid University 2008).

b) Critically Writing Papers is a Prerequisite Skill at Euclid University

According to Boileau Despréaux, a French poet translated into English by Raffel (2007, 26), we need to think deeply before **writing**. Precisely, in “The Art of Poetry,” he explained that conceptualization of ideas is the key to clarity in expression. The deeper and acuter you do the former, the easier, for the later, words come on their own.

To explore public health student's ideas conceptualization, formalization, and communication at EUCLID University, my “focus question” (UNSW 2019b) for the open assignment is: discuss, when **writing** a EUCLID's MIPH paper, if using a Word® template and **referencing** software along English guideline is supportive for expressing one's thoughts efficiently? I claim that obtaining the right substance, honoring elders, finding freedom within constraints, and enlightening readers is the way to proceed. To that extend, our “task, content and limiting word” (UNSW 2019a) are respectively “discuss, writing, and Euclid University.” If we use Williams (2013, 25) process to understand and adequately answer an essay's question, we can say that the “topic” of our **research question** is “writing a MIPH's paper,” and the “focus” is “EUCLID's guidelines.”

From my perspective, to correctly “write” during the MIPH at EUCLID, I’ll need substance along complying with guidelines; As for “discuss,” I will need to exchange ideas and points of view to learn or convince and be convinced by others. For anyone else, these two words may mean something else. For instance, in the academic setting, “discuss” means for UNSW (2019c) to “examine key points and possible interpretations, sift and debate, giving reasons for and against” but for Williams (2013, 29) he considers it as to “describe the similarities and differences between two or more things.” As for EUCLID (2019,1), it is the core process to develop a thesis.

In that regard, our way to discuss will be to investigate material identification and concepts integration according to different scholars worldwide versus the one from EUCLID who wrote or edited the first course materials. In the end, with that academic conversation formalized, we are going to share our perspectives on how we are going to enlightens the reader's knowledge. I’m intensely interested in this debate for two principal reasons: I need to improve my academic English formal communication skills toward publishing within the best African public health or management journal. Also, willing to become an independent consultant for various institutions like the World Health Organization (WHO), I need to upgrade my **critical** thinking skills for public health matters.

2) PREPARING TO DEVELOP MY PERSONALITY WITHIN EUCLID’S FRAMEWORK

I read two required documents from EUCLID. I am summarizing them here below. Then I engage with them. I aim to express my way of creating new substances from elder's experiences. I think it's good to honor them, for they help us evaluate our thoughts and find our way of making available our stone that contributes to creating the edifice of knowledge. EUCLID’s guidelines are our backbone to share our personal experiences toward preparing our new way to express our arguments, personality, and findings.

c) Summary of the Material Studied

To write this first response paper, I read the first compulsory documents for the first course that is ACA 401. These documents are namely, “how to write a response paper” and “ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1.” Cleenewerck and Gulma wrote or edited them. The former was published in April 2020, and it is a ten pages document. The latter was revised in 2019, and it is a sixty-six pages document. This last document complements the first and is more detailed in its approach to the recommendations and examples.

i) How to Write a Response Paper (RP)

The content of “[h]ow to write a response paper” is about EUCLID's (2020, 1) strong suggestion to formalize the most utilized interaction support between tutors and students, a response paper. The content is in two parts: the structure to write an RP and an

example from a Ph.D. candidate. In three pages, the first part explains and details each of the four sections within an RP at EUCLID: the material summary, reaction to the materials, conclusion, and references. It also explains how to quote both documents, regarding various contexts, and the file format to transmit to tutors. In six pages, the second part relates the point of view of a doctoral student preparing to formalize his final dissertation through the direction of EUCLID's recommended book. The book is namely "COMPLETING YOUR QUALITATIVE DISSERTATION: A ROAD MAP FROM BEGINNING TO END." It is written by Bloomberg and Volpe, in which the first edition is from 2008 (2020, 10). The student narrates its own experience and imbricates it with quotations from the book, a video, and a report.

The student's first name seems to be Michelle. She is passionate about art and works in law enforcement. She is trying to mix her theater and work experiences through an original dissertation's subject that should impact the officer's selection and training (2020, 6). In that regard, thanks to the book, she understood the process to elaborate a dissertation and stay physically and psychologically wealthy- to reach the doctoral goal: "reading, planning, writing, conducting a study, collecting and managing data, analyzing data and reporting findings, interpreting and synthesizing findings, and developing conclusions and recommendations" (Bloomberg and Volpe 2008, 1 cited in EUCLID 2020, 6).

In summary, that document, particularly the first section, is built to support students in showing off what they learned from imposed lectures and academically structure their thoughts about it through an RP format.

ii) *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*

The subject matter of "ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1" is about EUCLID's (2019, III-V) strong suggestion to write, mainly essays or RP, without **plagiarism** but by respecting some rules, based on literature reviews, through proper US English and Chicago **styles** pondered by "Latin abbreviations and expressions." The content is split into nine chapters. In terms of pages, the three longest are about **plagiarism**, essential differences between "American vs. British English," and the Chicago Manual of **Style** (CMS).

The first chapter, written by scholars from the University of New South Wales, sets recommendations that help students write good essays. To write efficiently means to sway the reader thanks to summarized academic evidence structured around a thesis and a statement that answers a question. In the second chapter and the beginning of the third, the authors explain that **plagiarism** is an intellectually banned behavior and how paraphrasing and **referencing** can avoid it. In the third chapter, the authors detail the process to critically stay focused, express ideas with simplicity, clarity, conciseness, and test the result by loud reading. The fourth chapter, namely "literature review," could broadly be called "basics of grammar lessons" because it reminds us of appropriate way to structure sentences and emphasize important information, to punctuate them, to use "and," "that/which," "its/it's," "your/you're," "good/weel," and "I/me." Concerning the fifth chapter, EUCLID (2019, 24) defined and summarized its **style** guide and language preference. For the former, "a **style** guide provides a means of documenting basic rules" that "is much more than just the

correct **usage** of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary.” EUCLID refers to Turabian et al.’s (2013) book “A MANUAL FOR WRITERS OF RESEARCH PAPERS, THESES, AND DISSERTATIONS.” We are today in the 8th edition, but chapter eight exposed an older edition. The leading lessons for us seem to be the differences between bibliography and parenthetical **referencing** processes and how to engage sources. For the later, EUCLID instead of British likes American English and therefore refers to Strunk and White (1999, 4) book, “THE ELEMENTS OF STYLE,” to support us understanding the “elementary rules of **usage**,” the “principles of composition,” “a few matters of form” as well as “words and expressions commonly misused.”

Coming back to that language preference, EUCLID formalized the sixth chapter around “[b]asic [d]ifferences and [i]nfluence of [c]hange” (2019, 27) between American and British English. It starts and closes on the punctuation matter, clarifying the importance of that concept. In between, it is about spelling, grammar, particular words, and community English varieties (e.g., African American). As for the seventh chapter, it is a commented example of a response paper. Precisely, in brackets are remarks or advice to optimize sentences to be more explicit, concise, direct, and to efficiently articulate arguments. Chapter eight, written by Dr. Abel Scribe, focuses on the CMS through three parts: **Style & usage**, page formatting, end/footnotes. The last chapter is about Latin abbreviation that helps to shade light, compare, or guide the reader. That chapter ninth mainly tables terms in Latin and its translation to English.

d) Substance Comes from Research

According to the WEBSTER’S NEW POCKET DICTIONARY (2009, 322), “substance” also means “central meaning.” To be central, things have to be surrounded by something else. That something else has to be defined before discovering what is central. That something else is what others think, and that center is what one’s think. To discover the former and the latter, reading is the must. To read, one has to look for what to read. Today, the Internet allows us to search for information, but any info is out there.

iii) Screened Online Information

According to EUCLID (2019, 7), you write in an academic **style** if you take stock of other writers, which is possible only after reading them with a rationale. In other words, “the citing of sources is fundamental to sound academic **writing**.” But to read efficiently, you need to look and find the right information, and to benefit from it, you need to summarize and later use it as evidence. To collect documents containing various academic knowledge, “the internet databases most frequently used for scientific **research** are PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar” (Watanabe 2019): Google Scholar is a free of charge source (Else 2018) as well as PubMed, but that last is tremendous for human sciences researchers; Google Scholar presents the most extensive view of the academic world in English (Delgado López-Cózar, Orduña-Malea, and Martín-Martín 2019; Lewandowski 2010, 3), and PubMed is the ideal web instrument in biomedical research (Falagas et al. 2008, 2); Scopus for the range of journals and Web of Sciences for quote analysis are two alternative’s subscription-based offers (Falagas et al. 2008, 5). As

for me, I like more and more screening the African Journals Online (AJOL) for it's "the world's largest and preeminent platform of African-published scholarly journals" (AJOL 1998).

iv) Reading Improves the Trustworthiness of the Substantiate

In an academic **research setting**, one reads what others have expressed to find and peek evidence to respond to a problem, said Williams (2013, 18). For Gastel and Day (2016, 233), it increases our "familiarity" with the subject. As for Itua et al. (2014, 316-317), the more we read academic material, the better chance we'll academically correctly write. This part of reading before writing is called "**literature review**" (LSHTM 2019, 5) even if for EUCLID (2019, 22), that concept seems more about **writing** proper English. When preparing the **literature review**, one has to select a suitable academic source material (Williams 2013, 11). Regarding the selection notion, texts are categorized as 'primary' or 'secondary' sources; the second is generally build on the primary (Williams 2013, 92). If there is a table of content, EUCLID (2019, 7) and A. Williams (2013, 93) suggest using it to go straight to the localized matter to be read. As for me, I like to define keywords and search for them through the whole text/article/textbook thanks to the tool "search" that you can activate with the combination of the keyboard "Ctrl+F."

e) Honor Elders

EUCLID (2019, 5) strongly advise to "avoid **Plagiarism**." This statement is preconized in the academic world and supported by students (Vardi 2012, 921) but hardly practiced in some professional activities like trading where I used to work. In the academic world, "avoiding **plagiarism**" (Harris 2014, 81) has many benefits, but takes a particular time that is seldom in trading of pharmaceutical raw material or as a consultant for the World Bank regarding terms of reference and concept notes formalization. During these job activities, **referencing** was sometimes considered as non-pragmatic or proof of lack of confidence.

Since avoiding **plagiarism** is a must in the academic world, one's needs to know what it is to take it into account better. The Oxford English Dictionary Online (2012, cited in Zhang 2016) reminds us that the word **plagiarism** comes from Latin and means 'to kidnap.' EUCLID (2019, 5) defines the term by not "giving credit to the author." Harris (2014, 81) has a slightly different approach around the labels "not properly" doing it. According to Grossberg (2008, 159), the concept of **plagiarism** has a "formal definition" since 1987 in history. The way it is defined concatenates both the EUCLID and Harris position. In Public Health research, James and Winter (2018, 247) added to EUCLID and Harris' notion the subtlety of "getting permission."

v) Good Referencing Avoids Plagiarism

To avoid **plagiarism**, EUCLID (2019, 6) strongly advise citing and listing. A **citation** could be done by quotation or paraphrasing and then listed through a bibliography

or **referencing** list. For the last concept, it could be performed through footnote and endnote or only endnote. The “parenthetical **citations**– reference list **style**” is the most used in social science (Turabian et al. 2007, 35). For Williams and Davis (2017,4), the essentials of **referencing** stand in seven words: “traceability, authority, credibility, reliability, reach and scope, politeness.” In summary, to avoid **plagiarism**, as stated by Pecorari (2013, 59-74), one’s needs to be transparent for the reader.

a. Zotero instead of Mendeley or EndNote

Nowadays, citing, listing, and **referencing** is much easier than years back, to my mind. Having done a thesis to obtain my PharmD diploma in 2005, **referencing** management software (RMS) (e.g., Zotero, Mendeley) did not exist or was not popularized as it is today. Most of all, there were no dedicated courses to learn about **referencing**. Thus, I only used the Word® approach to insert footnotes and endnotes with optimization toward the recommended University format. Today, RMS is widely used to download, store, arrange, and administer quotations/informations for many document formats (Y. Zhang 2012, 46). Four RMS tools were benchmarked by Zang, who consider that to decide which software is best for one’s needs, it is good to know their specification. The most popular are EndNote, Mendeley, and Zotero (Francavilla 2018, 1393). Since offering video training for better use of Zotero but not for the other RMS, we can consider that EUCLID favors the former, which is being developed by the George Mason University (Coar and Sewell 2010). I can understand EUCLID choice since Zotero has already significantly impacted students in acquiring **referencing** skills but not only (Kim 2011, 415). Also, Zotero users are more likely to come from the social sciences (Chen et al. 2018)

vi) *Critical Thinking Creates a Substance that Enlightens Knowledge*

Good “**referencing** guards against **plagiarism**” (EUCLID 2019, 4), in a Western approach; in an African one, I’ll say that **plagiarism** devastates roots connexion with elders. Good **referencing** also enlightens independent knowledge, thanks to **critical** thinkings (Vardi 2012, 925). Precisely, for Vardi, **referencing** is essential to start exhibiting “**critical** engagement.” For EUCLID (2019, 2), **critical** reflections are necessary for essay **writing** since it enlarges your ideas and helps one’s focus. It is effectively applied when different viewpoints are evaluated. **Critical** thinking is not patchwriting where quotation are concatenated together (Vardi 2012, 922) but a rational confrontation with other thoughts to better reveal one’s essence (2012, 923). Vardi (2012, 924) considers that it entails “evaluating, analyzing, interpreting and arguing,” and it can be magnified if “creativity” comes in to play (EUCLID 2019, 2). Meanwhile, considering EUCLID’s approach by using only two times in the text the wording “**critical** thinking” versus four times “avoid **plagiarism**,” we prefer Vardi’s suggestion for the advancement of **critical** thinking instead of avoiding **plagiarism**. In that regard, EUCLID should use much more time showing-off the former than the latter.

f) **Enlight Readers Above the Style**

Writing short sentences in the active form without generalities and complicated wording but focusing on the message is a way toward conciseness and clarity (EUCLID 2019, 14-16). Most of all, spare time using the provided EUCLID's Word® template when sharing RP to tutors is the minimum to do. It has to be done in adequation with the recommended Turabian formatting **styles** (44) crossed to Grammarly®'s vocabulary and grammatical audit. Within these limits is a place of freedom of expression and enlightenment.

vii) *Turabian Style Versus World Health Organization*

I obtained a PharmD and an MBA degree after dissertation defenses. For the latter, I used the American Psychological Association (APA) formatting **style** and either heard about CMS/Turabian or any other. APA was the one recommended by the university. Having screen both the "ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1" from EUCLID (2019) and "A MANUAL FOR WRITERS OF RESEARCH PAPERS, THESES, AND DISSERTATIONS: CHICAGO STYLE FOR STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS" from Turabian et al. (2007), I now understand the magnitude of the issue to handle to effectively write with full respect of a formatting **style**. Previously, I thought that only the **citation** and **referencing** were the main issue, but I'm noticing that concepts like abbreviation, capitalization, compound word, italic, number, and heading are other essential issues to pay attention to. I am discovering that only because I only studied in French, which is my mother's language. I assume I am mastering French language subtleties and have to learn the English one. In the meantime, I'm wondering why I can not write with the WHO formatting style instead of the Turabian one. I'm doing this EUCLID's MIPH with the vision to be a consultant for the WHO. In that regard, keeping in mind that one of the offered courses is "World Health Organization studies" (Euclid University 2008), I would have thought that the WHO formatting **style** will be the chosen **style** for the MIPH, but it seems not.

viii) *The First Impact of the EUCLID's Word® Template*

When formalizing my MBA's dissertation, only the front page, spacing, and font were constrained by a recommended format – along the APA **referencing style**. I had to create my heading **style**, and I enjoyed it. With EUCLID, the freedom to configure the page and heading format is minimal, and it helps us focus on the content, the substance, the arguments, and the wording flow. In a certain way, I like that approach. Thanks to the formatted template, I can focus on what I have to say and how I should say it to convince the reader. The Word® template as an expression platform provided by EUCLID already helped me support my professional communication. Precisely, I used it, after having optimized and customized it, to formalized a customer report.

3) CONCLUSION

Collecting academic information to elaborate one's thoughts toward formalizing a response paper about a MIPH's task at EUCLID was the purpose of this document. My way to fulfill the duty has been to discuss substance elaboration according to different academics versus Cleenewerck and Gulma (2019) guidelines. As students honoring scholars who are colossi's shoulders I am climbing (Merton 1965; Vernon 2017; Popova 2016), I used their words to express my point of view. I also discussed the various online database and displayed my choice for AJOL. As for the **literature review**, I explained how I screen documents thank the keywords search function. Turabian et al. (2007, 52) consider that "[s]ummarizing and paraphrasing are how we all gain control over new data, new and complicated ideas, even new ways of thinking," and I am empathic to that process. In that regard, I'd like to be more conciseness and creative and wonder how EUCLID will support me in that goal. Writing a EUCLID's MIPH response paper, using a Word® template and RMS along with strict English guideline and Grammarly®'s suggestion is supportive of complying with any formatting **style** - as long as one's can remind all of its detail. Technology is there and we dare not forget to use them to focus on the essential, that is, to formalize our reflection in the most efficient way and convince the reader to act or react.

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